

10TH ISAJ ANNUAL SYMPOSIUM 2019

INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY INNOVATIONS FOR
SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

SYMPOSIUM PROCEEDINGS

DECEMBER 9, 2019

VENUE

Osaka University Hall,
Toyonaka campus
Osaka University, Osaka

Organizers

ISAJ
INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN

ISAJ is registered as a Japanese non-profit organization (NPO) under Japan's NPO law. Tsukuba has been decided to be ISAJ's headquarter. The Executive Body is ISAJ's governing body and is responsible for directing the affairs and determining the future of the Society. The Executive Body will appoint some of the Executive Body members to take responsibilities such as the Chapter Presidents of six different regions in Japan (Hokkaido, Tohoku, Tokyo, Tsukuba, Fukuoka, and Osaka). The election for the Office bearers (Chairman, Vice-Chairman, Secretary, and Assistant Secretary, Chief-Editor, Associate-Editor, and Treasurer) will be held biennially, and all the members of the society can take part in the election process.

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10th ISAJ Symposium-2019

On

Interdisciplinary S&T Innovations for Sustainable Society

Convener:

Dr. Mahendra Kumar Pal

Co-conveners:

Dr. Golap Kalita

Dr. Rajiv Kumar Verma

Organizing committee:

Dr. Sunil Kaul

Dr. Alok Singh

Dr. Kedar Mahapatra

Dr. Swadhin Behera

Prof. D. Sakthi Kumar

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10th ISAJ Symposium

Interdisciplinary Science and Technology Innovations for Sustainable Society

December 9, 2019 (Monday)

Venue:

Osaka University Hall, Toyonaka Campus, Osaka University, Osaka

PROGRAM

8:30 - 9:00	Registration
09:00 - 09:05	Lighting of the Lamp
Aspiring Young Researcher Session (12+3 Min) Chair: Rumpa Pal	
9:05 - 9:10	<i>Remarks</i> Mahendra Kr. Pal , Symposium convener
9:10 - 9:30	<i>Plenary Lecture</i> Masami Kojima , AIST Kansai Center. Reduction in BDNF from inefficient precursor conversion influences nest building and promotes depressive behavior in mice
9:30 - 9:45	Sharath Srinivasamurthy , Osaka Prefecture University, Osaka. Multi-connection VAWT: A novel solution to harness offshore wind energy.
9:45 - 10:00	Naoko Ikeo , Kobe University, Kobe Evaluation of <i>in-vitro</i> fatigue properties of Mg-Ca alloy with fine grains.
10:00 - 10:15	Netranand Sahu , Kyoto University, Kyoto. Climate variability and its ramification on river hydrology.
10:15 - 10:30	Tea/Coffee Break#1

Student Session #1 (7+3 Min) Chair: Sharath Srinivasamurthy	
10:30 - 10:40	Subhankar Bera , Osaka Prefecture University, Osaka. Common physiology of different host-parasitic plant complexes is controlled by mobile sRNAs.
10:40 - 10:50	Rohit Divyesh , Kyushu University, Kyushu. Site reconnaissance of long-distance ground flow in Sulawesi, Indonesia due to September 28, 2018 Sulawesi earthquake.
10:50 - 11:00	Radhika Biyani , School of Materials Science, JAIST, Japan. Identification of the Inhibitory Activity of HIV-1 Reverse Transcriptase in the Extracts of Indian Plants.
11:00 - 11:10	Trishit Banerjee , Tohoku University, Sendai. Engineering of genome editing protein Cas9 that slides along DNA faster and might enable efficient target search.
11:10 - 11:20	Madhu Malinee , Kyoto University, Kyoto. Targeted suppression of the metastasis regulatory transcription factor SOX2 in various cancer cell lines using a sequence-specific designer pyrrole-imidazole polyamide.
3-Min Thesis Challenge Chair: Chaitra Chandrashekar	
11:20 - 11:35	Alok Kumar , Kyoto University, Kyoto. Tumors attenuating the mitochondrial activity in T cells escape from PD-1 blockade therapy. Sai Veerya Mahadevan , Osaka University, Osaka. Designing primitive recursive function-based domain specific programming languages. Siddharth Gavhale , Kyoto University, Kyoto. Simulation of particles evolution by mean curvature flow. Nikesh Narang , Osaka University, Osaka Phenylketonuria inspired amino acid self-assembly model and its applications
11:35 - 12:00	Poster Session
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch and Poster Session

Keynote Session Chair: Mahendra Kr. Pal	
13:00 - 13:10	<i>Welcome Address</i> Sunil Kaul , Chairman, ISAJ Mahendra Kr. Pal , Symposium convener
13:10 - 13:20	<i>Inaugural Address</i> H.E. Sanjay Kumar Verma , The Ambassador of India to Japan.
13:20 - 13:50	<i>Keynote Address #1</i> Kazuhiko Nakatani , Osaka University, Osaka. Small molecules targeting repeat sequences causing neurological disorders.
13:50 - 14:00	<i>Special Address</i> H.E. B. Shyam , Consul General of India, Osaka-Kobe.
14:00 - 14:30	<i>Keynote Address #2</i> Hiroshi Sugiyama , Kyoto University, Kyoto. Chemical biology of nucleic acids: DNA origami and artificial genetic switch.
14:30 - 14:35	<i>Remarks</i> Usha Dixit , Counsellor (S&T), Embassy of India.
14:35 - 14:40	<i>Vote of Thanks</i> Kedarnath Mahapatra , General Secretary, ISAJ
14:40 - 15:00	Tea/Coffee Break#2 & Group Photo
Plenary Session (15+5 Min) Chair: Kedarnath Mahapatra	
15:00 - 15:20	<i>Plenary#1</i> Sudhir Krishna , National Centre for Biological Sciences, Bangalore, India. Interdisciplinary team building to tackle 21st century viral challenges in India and Africa.
15:20 - 15:40	<i>Plenary #2</i> Hemanta Hazarika , Kyushu University, Kyushu. Some novel approaches towards sustainable construction for climate change adaptation.
15:40 - 16:00	<i>Plenary #3</i> Sarat K. Sahoo , QST, Tokyo. Fukushima-Daiichi nuclear power station accident: A rapid method for the measurement of 90sr as a challenge in Fukushima samples.

Invited Lecture Session #1 (12+3 Min) Chairs: Golap Kalita and Rajiv Kumar Verma	
16.00 - 16.15	Mototada Shichiri , AIST Kansai Center, Osaka α -Tocopherol deficiency protects mice against malaria infection.
16.15 - 16.30	Raj Kumar Kalra , AIST, Tsukuba. Alternative inhibition of EGFR and TGF- β signaling in Oral cancer: Therapeutic efficacy of Ashwagandha and Gefitinib -based combinatorial approach.
16.30 - 16.45	P.K. Hashim , University of Tokyo, Tokyo. Supramolecular chemistry for Bio-applications: Designed nanocarriers for gene and protein delivery.
16.45 - 17.00	Rajesh Kumar , Toyohashi University of Technology, Nagoya. Graphene derivatives modification as defect-engineered mesoporous electrode materials in energy storage/conversion devices.
17:00 - 17:15	Tea/Coffee Break #3
Invited Lecture Session #2 (12+3 Min) Chair: P. K. Hashim and Raj Kumar Kalra	
17:15 - 17:30	Tomomi Tani , AIST Kansai Center, Osaka Listening to the mechanism of life through advanced polarized light microscopy
17:30 - 17:45	Lokesh P. Tripathi , National Institute of Biomedical Innovations, Health and Nutrition (NIBIOHN), Osaka. Integrative network-based and multi-omics data analysis for biological knowledge discovery.
17:45 - 18:00	Bhaskar Dasgupta , RIKEN, Kobe. Probing dynamical behavior of biomolecules expediting understanding of molecular functions.
18:00 - 18:15	Rumpa Pal , University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba. The metallic bond in Aluminium: Quantum crystallography.
18:15 - 18:30	Concluding Session & Awards Session Golap Kalita and Rajiv Kumar Verma, Co-convener(s)

भारत के राजदूत
AMBASSADOR OF INDIA

भारत का राजदूतावास
Embassy of India
2-2-11 Kudan Minami, Chiyoda-ku
Tokyo 102 0074

I am happy to learn that the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is going to organize its Tenth Symposium at the Osaka University on December 09, 2019.

The Embassy has supported ISAJ since its inception. It is a forum that enables young Indian researchers and students to gain a broader perspective by connecting with scientists and research institutions in Japan. This year's theme is aptly titled "Interdisciplinary Science and Technology Innovations for Sustainable Society". The theme has a great relevance to contemporary issues both in India and Japan and I believe that the new knowledge derived and exchanged among the disciplines and across the institutions would help finding innovative solutions for some of the challenges faced by the mankind and the environment.

I sincerely hope that the scientific deliberations during the symposium would lead to more constructive recommendations for enhancing strategic collaborations between the two countries.

I wish the Symposium a grand success.

(Sanjay Kumar Verma)
Ambassador of India

Tokyo
2 December 2019

We, on behalf of the ISAJ, would like to take this opportunity to sincerely welcome all the delegates and guests to the 10th Annual Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) on Interdisciplinary Science and Technology for Safety and Quality of Life. We are happy to celebrate the 10th anniversary of ISAJ this year as a Non-profit Organization (NPO). At the end of 2008, it was initially conceived as a community forum by coming together of many Indian scientists working in Japan. In January 2009, it was formally inaugurated by Prof. R. Chidambaram, the then Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government, in the presence of His Excellency, the then Ambassador of India, and the next year it was formalized as a registered NPO in Japan. ISAJ has its functional chapters at Hokkaido, Sendai, Tsukuba, Tokyo, Kyoto, and Kobe that have been promoting seminars, free discussions, and networking at all levels. Apart from that, ISAJ has been focusing on networking among Indian scientists and researchers in Japan and serves as a strong bridge for India-Japan Science & Technology exchanges. It has been helping several young Indian students to get professional training and settling in Japan.

ISAJ has been organizing the India-Japan symposium every year, to showcase the research being carried out by Indian researchers and their colleagues in Japan. The first seven annual symposia were held at the Main Auditorium of the Embassy of India in Tokyo, the eighth one in Tokyo University, and the ninth in AIST, Tsukuba. This year, the tenth symposium is being held in Osaka, in the view of a rapidly increasing Indian research community in the Kansai region. In every annual symposium, we have strived to make this event interdisciplinary, allowing wide participation and exchange of ideas and experiences beyond any theme boundaries. Likewise, this year, we have selected the theme entitled “Interdisciplinary Science and Technology Innovations for Sustainable Society” keeping in mind the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015. We genuinely believe that this is a unique opportunity to interact and learn beyond our specialized domains and to innovate our thoughts and research outcomes to the benefit of science and society. We also hope that this platform benefits young Indian students and researchers, and they enjoy interacting with each other and senior professionals both from India and Japan. We take this opportunity to welcome our guests, especially the young researchers from India, and are looking forward to free interactions over the poster presentations. Young researcher’s session has been the highlight of all the earlier symposia. This year too, we are looking forward to hearing from many young researchers on their work and pathway to success in Japan.

We are grateful to His Excellency Mr. Sanjay Kumar Verma, Ambassador of India to Japan and Dr. Usha Dixit, S&T Counsellor, and other dignitaries for joining us in celebrating this year's 10th-anniversary annual symposium. We are sincerely thankful to all the guests and participants for taking the time to join us and present their work. We believe that it is an excellent opportunity for us to interact with each other and strengthen India-Japan S&T ties. We sincerely hope that we all will enjoy the symposium that will further inspire India-Japan collaborations and friendships in Science & Technology.

With best regards,

Sunil Kaul
Chairman, ISAJ

Alok Singh
Vice-Chairman, ISAJ

Kedar Mahapatra
General Secretary, ISAJ

CONVENORS' WELCOME MESSAGE

It has been a great pleasure for us to convene the 10th ISAJ symposium entitled **Interdisciplinary Science and Technology Innovation for Sustainable Society**. Theme of symposium has been determined by keeping the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by United Nations members in 2015. Interdisciplinary nature of symposium allows wide spectrum of participation and interactive discussions beyond any theme boundary.

It is an honor and privilege to have with us high-level dignitaries, top scientists and researchers from both countries from Japan and India as well as other nations. Today, wide spectrum of themes related to Science and Technological innovations will be covered. Symposium is comprising of Inaugural Session, Keynote Session, Plenary Session, Invited Talk, Aspiring Young Researcher Session and Student Session with Oral and Poster presentation. We have also introduced a new session for students named "three-minute thesis challenge". We are sure that each participant will identify the subject of his/her interest and will benefit from many fruitful and enriching discussions.

We take immense pleasure to recognize the growing collaborations between India and Japan under bilateral as well as multilateral frameworks. India and Japan have historical relationships through exchanges of culture and heritage. With rapid progresses in science and technology, Japan is established as one of the leading centers in the world for scientific research. This excellent research environment has already benefited many of us. By further strengthening the growing scientific collaborations between Japan and India, we can address some of the global challenges and human securities. Symposium will enable the scientists to reflect on how different disciplines of science, engineering, and technology can be better integrated towards creating innovative solutions to the sustainability challenges.

We are humbled with the gracious presence of H. E. Mr. Sanajay Kumar Verma, Ambassador of India to Japan, H.E. Mr. B. Shyam, Consul General of India Osaka-Kobe and Dr. Usha Dixit, S&T Counsellor, Embassy of India, Tokyo at our symposium. We would like to sincerely thank to all Keynote Speakers, Plenary Speakers, Invited Speakers, Students, colleagues and friends, who are showcasing our research achievements and representing many prominent universities and research institutes.

We congratulate you all for your commitment and participation and wish you the success.

With best regards,

Mahendra Kumar Pal
(Convener)

Golap Kalita
(Co-convener)

Rajiv Kumar Verma
(Co-convener)

Keynote Lectures

Keynote Lectures

KL01:

Chemical Biology of Nucleic Acids: DNA Origami and Artificial Genetic Switch

Hiroshi Sugiyama

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The DNA origami method developed for the preparation of fully addressable two-dimensional (2-D) structures has been utilized for the selective positioning of the functional molecules and nanoparticles. We designed "DNA frame" using the DNA origami method to investigate enzymatic action and DNA structural change.^[1] To observe the behaviors and reactions of DNA methyltransferase, DNA recombinase, Cas9, MOC1, and DNA repair enzymes, the substrate dsDNAs were incorporated into the cavity of the DNA frame, and the enzymes that bound to the target dsDNA were observed using high speed-atomic force microscope.^[1,2] We recently developed DNA nanocages^[1,2] and investigated the effect of confined space on the property of G-quadruplex and found that mechanical and thermodynamic stabilities of the G-quadruplex inside the nanocage are significantly increased.^[3] Also a strategy for lipid-bilayer-assisted self-assembly of various DNA origami tiles into 2-D lattices was developed.^[4]

Our group also have been undertaking original research on the molecular recognition of DNA by antitumor antibiotics, and the analysis of atom-specific chemical reaction on DNA. By reconstituting such knowledge, various functionalized sequence-specific DNA binding pyrrole-imidazole polyamides (PIPs) were synthesized as an artificial genetic switch, which can switch on and switch off the gene expression on demand. We recently developed alkylating PIP that could switches off cancer related KRAS gene^[5] and RUNX 1-3 controlling genes.^[6,7] To switch on the gene expression we need to consider Epigenetics. We developed a SAHA-PIP containing sequence-specific pyrrole-imidazole polyamides (PIPs) and HDAC

inhibiting SAHA. Evaluation of the effect of SAHA-PIPs on genome-wide gene expression in human dermal fibroblasts (HDFs) divulged that each SAHA-PIP could differentially activate the therapeutically important genes.^[8] Conjugation of DNA binding domain of 'I' with HAT activating CTB remarkably activated identical cluster of genes as SAHA-PIP 'I' to substantiate the role of PIP in sequence-specific gene regulation.^[9] Recently we introduced bromodomain inhibitor to PIP to activate gene expression in sequence-specific manner.^[10] To extend recognition sequence, we introduce host-guest system to facilitate cooperative binding to target sequence even in cellular condition.^[11] In this talk recent progress of DNA origami technology and regulation of the gene expression using designed PIPs will be discussed.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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KL02:

Small Molecules targeting Repeat Sequences causing Neurological Disorders

Kazuhiko Nakatani

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The expansion of trinucleotide repeat (TNR) is causative of more than 40 hereditary neurological disorders. The CAG sequence in the coding region of protein huntingtin for the patients of Huntington disease is 40~100 repeats, whereas that is about 6~36 repeats for healthy individuals. The aberrant and enormous expansion of the CTG sequence of 5~38 repeat in 3'-UTR of the DMPK gene up to 40~1000 repeats was observed for the patients of Myotonic Dystrophy type 1. The mechanism of CAG repeat expansion and contraction involves the non-canonical hairpin secondary structures (slip out). The slip out structures contains many X-X mismatched base pairs flanked by two C-G base pairs. Recent studies revealed that not only DNA repeats but also the transcript, RNA repeats, are toxic to the cells. We have focused our attention on the small organic molecules selectively binding to these DNA and RNA repeats. In the presentation, our recent results on targeting TNR and other repeats by small molecules will be discussed.

References

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2. Modulating RNA secondary and tertiary structures by mismatch binding ligands. Murata, A.; Nakamori, M.; Nakatani, K. *Methods* **2019**, 167, 78-91. doi: 10.1016/j.ymeth.2019.05.006.
3. A dimeric 2,9-diamino-1,10-phenanthroline derivative improves alternative splicing in myotonic dystrophy type 1 cell and mouse models. Li, J.; Nakamori, M.; Matsumoto, J.; Murata, A.; Dohno, C.; Kiliszek, A.; Taylor, K.; Sobczak, K.; Nakatani, K. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2018**, 24, 18115-18122. 10.1002/chem.201804368.

Plenary Lectures

PL01:

Inter disciplinary team building to tackle 21st century viral challenges in India and Africa

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Our primary interest is in cervical cancers: a papillomavirus driven malignancy of major public health significance in both India and Africa. We have focused on identifying the signaling pathways that complement the function of papillomavirus oncogenes. In particular, we have delineated the role of Notch signaling in driving human cervical cancer progression [1].

The talk will cover some of the background and the drug design challenges ahead. The above program is primarily funded by TIFR and DBT.

Our other interest is in Dengue viruses and we have obtained a 3 year grant from Narayana Murthy, co-founder Infosys, to enable the development of a novel Dengue vaccine. We have undertaken a fairly large scale sequencing analysis across the country of Dengue genomes and are currently designing novel vaccine constructs.

In parallel, in Nairobi, we have set up a pathogen capacity effort to support the program called nano-pore sequence training [2].

Tackling 21st century viruses, will require inter disciplinary teams of bio-informatics, computer experts, virologists, health systems specialists all working together and I will describe some of our efforts in nucleating such teams in both India and Africa.

Reference

1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yexcr.2019.111682>
2. <https://kavi-icr.uonbi.ac.ke/content/nanopore-sequencing-training>

PL02:

Some Novel Approaches towards Sustainable Construction for Climate Change Adaptation

Hemanta Hazarika

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Recently, concerns are growing regarding climate change induced disasters associated with global warming, and the approaches and efforts to reduce emissions of CO₂, have been implemented through the collaboration of industry, government and academia. The recycling of the waste discharged by either human or industrial activities as geomaterials is one of these approaches. However, rather than mere recycling, Cascaded Recycling of such products are encouraged these days as it leads to substantial reduction of CO₂ emission to the atmosphere. Fig. 1 explains the concept of cascaded recycle in the case of waste tire recycling. In Japan, the volume of waste tires generated in the year 2018 has been increased by more than 2 million from the previous year. The trend of recycling efforts during 2009 ~ 2017 shows that at least 59% of the scrap tires were used for energy recovery (thermal recycling). The rests were reused either through returning on the same product (material recycling) or through returning on different products (cascaded recycling).

Fig. 1. Concept of Cascaded Recycling of Waste Tires

Global statistics on waste tires also presents a similar scenario. About 1 billion waste tires are generated every year in different parts of the world. Most of those waste tires are either burnt to produce energy or landfilled. Thermal recycling, however, is harmful to the environment because it releases more CO₂ compared to the other efforts of recycling, such as material recycling and cascaded recycling. In order to

encourage the recycling of waste tires that minimizes the CO₂ release, utilization of such industrial by-product in cascaded form (returning on different product) is gaining attention in recent years. It is, therefore, necessary to shift the share of recycling from thermal to cascaded recycling. When recycled in cascaded form they can be called tire derived geo-materials (TDGM). Besides the low-carbon release potential of such materials when used as geomaterials, the other advantageous material characteristics of TDGM are: they are light weight, they have excellent vibration absorption capacity and they possess high permeability. In addition, these materials are non-dilatant in nature unlike other granular geomaterials. Owing to these characteristics, they can replace other conventional materials (such as gravel), in applications such as drainage, leachate, reinforcement, and so on.

On the other hand, in recent years, the world has seen large scale earthquake induced hazards or climate change related hazards. Especially, in Japan, such natural hazards are too frequent in recent years. Also, in most of the developing countries, where the infrastructure development is still in infancy, adequate and cost-effective disaster mitigation efforts are urgently needed for sustainable construction. The key issues in most of the developing countries, are the balance between the cost and the increased burden to environment, while undertaking any infrastructural projects.

In this lecture, recycling of waste tires and disaster mitigation in the context of Japanese experiences were focused, and few geo-disaster reduction techniques developed in Japan using TDGM are explained.

PL03:

**FUKUSHIMA DAIICHI NUCLEAR POWER STATION
ACCIDENT: A RAPID METHOD FOR THE MEASUREMENT
OF ^{90}Sr AS A CHALLENGE IN FUKUSHIMA SAMPLES**

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On 11 March 2011, the so-called "the 2011 Great East Japan Earthquake" and Tsunami struck the northeast coast of Japan, which resulted in widespread injury and loss of life. This natural disaster caused a severe accident in Fukushima Dai-ichi nuclear power station (FDNPS). As a result, large amounts of fission products like (^{131}I , ^{132}Te , ^{137}Cs , ^{90}Sr isotopes, traces of actinides etc.) released into environment [1]. The released radionuclides, typically ^{131}I and radiocesium, had been globally measured in environmental samples. However, after the initial emission in March 2011, the atmospheric emission rates of the FDNPS-derived radionuclides decreased rapidly.

Although eight years have passed from the FDNPS accident, the Japanese government, research institutes, and universities are continuously monitoring the FDNPS derived radionuclides in the atmosphere, marine, and environmental samples. Major target nuclides are ^{134}Cs , ^{137}Cs , and ^{90}Sr due to their long radioactive half-lives and potential possibility of post-accident releases [2].

Typically, fission products are neutron-rich isotopes emitting beta particles that are released from the nucleus to attain a stable isotope configuration. This decay process is typically accomplished with gamma-ray emission; therefore, gamma-ray spectroscopy is applied primarily for the determination of the fission products in samples affected by the nuclear accident. However, a few fission products such as ^{90}Sr , ^{89}Sr are pure beta emitters. ^{90}Sr ($t_{1/2} = 28.8$ y) is one of the most common and hazardous fission products released by a nuclear reactor. Furthermore, the ^{90}Sr has a long biological half-life (~ 18 y) in the human body. Due to its chemical similarity to calcium, it accumulates in bones and irradiates bone marrow, causing high radio-toxicity. Therefore, to assess ^{90}Sr is important in case of a nuclear disaster.

Measurement of ^{90}Sr using radiometric methods is a time-consuming process since it involves complex sample preparation and analytical separation required to produce reliable data. In our laboratory, a novel method was developed for ^{90}Sr analysis using thermal ionization mass spectrometry (TIMS) [3,4]. This novel method was successfully applied for ^{90}Sr measurement first time in the history of inorganic mass-spectrometry in a worldwide open proficiency test (IAEA-TEL 2017-3) conducted by IAEA. The ^{90}Sr concentration of tap water (2.20 ± 0.06 fg·g⁻¹) and milk powder (19.6 ± 1.0 fg·g⁻¹) samples were analysed in the proficiency test and an 'accepted' status was gained for both accuracy (relative bias of 4.2 % and 2.1 %, respectively) and precision (relative uncertainty of 3.1 % and 5.7 %, respectively).

This novel method is robust and has significant advantages over radiometric techniques that will be helpful not only in the monitoring of radionuclides in the atmosphere as well as the marine environment but also to distinguish whether it is due to anthropogenic or natural events.

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PL04:

Reduction in BDNF from inefficient precursor conversion influences nest building and promotes depressive behavior in mice

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We generated a knock-in mouse line in which the gene encoding brain-derived neurotrophic factor (*Bdnf*) was replaced with a sequence for proBDNF containing human single-nucleotide polymorphisms encoding arginines proximal to the cleavage site (R125M and R127L). The levels of the mature form of BDNF in hippocampal tissue lysates were decreased in a manner dependent on the number of copies of the mutant gene, indicating that the mutations inhibited proteolytic conversion of proBDNF into mature BDNF. Although homozygous mice had a proBDNF/BDNF ratio of ~9:1, they survived until adulthood. Heterozygous mutant mice, in which BDNF levels were 50% of those in wild-type littermates, exhibited stronger depression-like behaviors and gained more weight when housed in social isolation, suggesting that impaired proBDNF cleavage contributes to stress-induced depression. Unexpectedly, socially isolated heterozygous mice displayed a pronounced deficit in daily nest-building behaviors. These findings suggest that BDNF plays a crucial role in the daily activities of mice and influences susceptibility to depression.

Invited Talks

IT01:

Supramolecular Chemistry for Bio-applications: Designed Nanocarriers for Gene and Protein Delivery

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In this talk, I am hoping to introduce novel designs based on supramolecular chemistry (non-covalent interaction between molecules), which could be used as ‘nanocarriers’ for the delivery of biomacromolecules such as nucleic acids and proteins. Small molecule-based drugs (e.g. paracetamol, doxorubicin for chemotherapy etc.) cure many of the diseases, however, only less than 20% of the diseases are known to be ‘druggable’ by such drugs, in addition to the severe side effects. An alternate approach is to use gene or protein as therapeutic drugs, which can cure any diseases including cancers, Alzheimers etc. One crucial problem with the gene- or protein-based drug is its instability in the bloodstream, where the drug mostly cleaved by enzymes or proteases before reaching the diseased site. Hence, nanocarriers to ‘carry’ a drug from outside the body into the desired site of drug action are necessary for an effective therapeutic application. Important points to be considered are; the drug should be non-covalently encapsulated into the ‘carrier’, should protect in the bloodstream and deliver the drug at the diseased site by some stimuli.

One of our approaches constitutes a ‘template polymerization’, i.e. a guanidinium ions (Gu^+)- monomer with thiol termini adhere non-covalently to a small interfering RNA surface (a therapeutic gene fragment) and form a ‘caplet’ via disulfide polymerization. This RNA/polymer complexes (nanocaplets) effectively penetrated into the cancer cells and knocked down the target gene.¹⁻³ By using this concept of ‘template polymerization’, we also have prepared protein-nanocaplets with different proteins (BSA, Cytochrome C, β -galactosidase), which found application in intracellular protein delivery. In a second approach, we have constructed a chaperonin nanotube consisting of an array of RNA at its interior. In the presence of a mixture of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and glutathione stimuli, this nanotube cleaved to release the RNA drug. We are confident that this responsive virus-like nanocarrier can efficiently deliver a cargo RNA inside a cell for knocking down the protein expression *in vivo*. In a third approach, by using supramolecular interaction, we are now constructing a porous architecture based on a three-component system (chaperonin protein, DNA and nanoparticle).

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IT02:

Alternative inhibition of EGFR and TGF- β signalings in Oral Cancer: Therapeutic efficacy of Ashwagandha and Gefitinib -based combinatorial approach

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EGFR and TGF- β pathways have been the major driver oncogenic signalings that contribute to a significant rate of mortality in aggressive Oral cancers. Although, a number of synthetic inhibitors/drugs have been identified to specifically inhibit the above signalings, risks of non-specificity and acquired drug-resistance by cancer cell remained the major therapeutic hurdle. Therefore, finding the efficient and safer therapeutic option has become the key requisite of a promising alternative. Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) is herbal medicinal plant, and inhabitant of Indian Subcontinent. Ashwagandha is source of potent bioactive compounds including withaferin A, withanone and 3 β -methoxy withaferin A. In the present report, we investigated combinatorial efficacy of Ashwagandha extracts along with Gefitinib (a potent EGFR inhibitor) against oral cancer. Taking the HSC3 (EGFR+, SMAD-/-, CyclinD1+, PI3Kmut, p44+) and SAT (TGFB+, SMAD+, pAkt+) oral cancer cell lines, we investigated differential modulation of these oncogenic signalings on individual and combinatorial treatment. We found that Gefitinib treatment in HSC3 (EGFR+) cells alternatively activate TGF/p44/ β -catenin-cyclin D1 signaling for survival, but K2CD (Ashwagandha extract) treatment attenuated activation of above alternative signaling and lead to cell death. The common target protein (pAkt, Cyclin D1, and β -catenin) downstream to EGFR and TGF- β signalings were found to acquire the survival advantage in oral cancer cells on alternative inhibition. Therefore, these results suggested that combination of Gefitinib with bioactive/extracts of Ashwagandha (retaining both the properties of Gefitinib and *Withania somnifera*), could be an efficient therapeutic approach against oral cancer.

IT03:

Graphene derivatives modification as defect-engineered mesoporous electrode materials in energy storage/conversion devices

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Graphene is as exciting carbon based 2D materials considered as one of the most promising and novel candidate of energy storage/ conversion systems. It contains high surface area, extraordinary electrical and thermal conductivity, high mechanical flexibility and chemical stability. Reduced graphene oxide as major derivatives of graphene synthesized by oxidation and reduction of graphite is highly utilized in electrode materials to improve the performance of energy storage/ conversion. The performances of energy storage/ conversion are highly depending upon nature of electrode materials. The electrode design requires large amount of high surface area containing porous active materials which can be achieved from highly reduced graphene oxide. Large amount of graphene oxide can be easily prepared at low cost by chemical oxidation of graphite and its reduction by various approaches (chemical, microwave, laser, thermal etc.). Reduced graphene oxide contains layered structure (along with small oxygen functionalities) with high surface area which plays a crucial role in electrode materials. Compared to reduced graphene oxide, modified reduced graphene oxide (by metal oxide/ conducting polymer with reduced graphene oxide) is studied as improved electrode materials in energy storage because of its defective nature as well as small amount of negatively oxygen functionalities help to attached metal oxide/ polymer. Modified graphene derivatives for hybrids/ nanocomposites formation using metal oxides/mixed metal oxides and metal sulfides/mixed metal sulphides, it shows a profound impact on the performance of energy storage devices.

IT04:

α -Tocopherol deficiency protects mice against malaria infection

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The emergence of malaria pathogens having resistance against antimalarials implies the necessity for the development of new drugs. It has been reported in clinical research that α -tocopherol deficiency protected malaria infection. α -Tocopherol is a most active form of vitamin E, a lipid-soluble antioxidant. We have demonstrated a resistance against malaria infection of α -tocopherol deficient mice showing undetectable plasma levels of α -tocopherol. However, dietary restriction induced α -tocopherol deficiency is difficult to be applied as a clinical antimalarial therapy. On the other hand, we found that probucol, the antihyperlipidemic drug, had the effect of reducing α -tocopherol in mouse plasma. Here, we report on a new strategy to potentially treat malaria by using probucol. Probuco pre-treatment for 2 weeks and treatment throughout the infection rescued from death of mice infected with *Plasmodium yoelii* XL-17 or *P. berghei* ANKA. In addition, survival was extended when the treatment started immediately after parasite inoculation. The ratio of lipid peroxidation products to parent lipids increased in plasma after 2 weeks treatment of probucol. This indicates that the protective effect of probucol might be mediated by the oxidative stressful environment induced by α -tocopherol deficiency. Probuco in combination with dihydroartemisin suppressed the proliferation of *P. yoelii* XL-17. α -Tocopherol in host circulation is necessary for malaria parasites to protect themselves from oxidative stress. It has been described that the malaria parasite is sensitive to oxidative stress. Remarkably, malaria parasites lack catalase and glutathione peroxidase, the major antioxidant enzymes in eukaryotes. These results indicated that probucol might be a candidate for a drug against malaria infection by inducing α -tocopherol deficiency without dietary α -tocopherol restriction.

IT05:

Integrative network-based and multi-omics data analysis for biological knowledge discovery

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Precision (also stratified or personalized) medicine promises new and specifically tailored medical care for individuals or groups of patients characterized by clinical and laboratory information, health records, lifestyle or demographic factors. A detailed understanding of disease mechanisms will enable us to pinpoint novel targets for the development of new treatments and biomarkers that tell us more about disease progression and response to treatment within appropriate patient groups.

The proliferation of genome-scale (omics) datasets offers unprecedented opportunities in discovering novel biological functions, interpreting genotype-phenotype relationships and understanding disease mechanisms. These data are also challenging to analyses and interpret. Therefore, bioinformatics methods that leverage various biological datatypes within a multi-omics data analysis framework are critical to unravelling the organization of cellular networks that govern the functioning of the cellular machinery.

Such approaches also empower the researchers to identify genes, pathways, and networks that drive complex biological systems and diseases such as cancer and for developing clinically relevant outcomes.

IT06:

**Probing dynamical behavior of biomolecules expediting
understanding of molecular functions**

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Biological systems are complex because they encode a huge amount of information in a string of alphabets. This requires a systematic flow of information from gene to protein. By coordinated interaction between proteins certain characteristics of the living organism are manifested. For the robust interaction between two protein molecules their three-dimensional structures are required. While that is enough in many cases, a dynamic viewpoint is often necessary for a more concrete understanding of molecular function. There can be many ways of adding dynamic information that help to underpin functional details of different levels. For example, molecules can be blindly simulated to generate thousands of structures and then analyzed to recover a pattern. Or a molecule can be thought of a collection of springs between atoms and its vibrational patterns are analyzed. Sometimes a more complicated method of simulation is used to generate structures following some particular rules. Recently, simulations are designed directly to aid experimental observations – so called hybrid modelling. Here, some of the useful methods will be introduced with their application.

IT07:

The metallic bond in Aluminium: Quantum Crystallography

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Aluminum is considered as simple metal and its electronic distribution is expected to resemble free electron model. However, tight binding type features have been reported in recent accurate experimental studies on aluminium.^{1,2} A deeper understanding of experimental data would help us to interpret the electron distribution and chemical bonding scenario in metallic aluminium.^{3,4} Within the framework of CRYSTAL14 package⁵, using atom centered Gaussian type basis sets for the metallic aluminium, we have investigated the effect of additional d and f functions⁶ on x-ray structure factors and electron density features. Specially the low order structure factors are affected by additional d, f functions (Figure 1a). And there is an indication of core deformation at Aluminum centers (Figure 1b). However, still the experimental pattern couldn't be satisfactorily reproduced only with addition of polarizable functions in the basis set.

In this context, quantum crystallography⁷ aims for improving the theory by enhancing the information content of the wave function from experimental data. The most popular X-ray constrained wave function (XCW) fitting⁸ is promising for molecular crystals, but not so well studied for conducting systems, only Beryllium metal⁹ has been reported till date.

Thus, XCW fitting for conducting Aluminium would be ideal for investigating weak metallic bonding.

Figure 1: Effect of d and f functions on (a) theoretical x-ray structure factors; (b) Deformation density for metallic Aluminium (CRYSTAL14 package); (c) X-ray constrained wave function (XCW) fitting: χ^2 agreement statistics for x-ray structure factors vs. Lagrange fitting parameter, λ

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IT08:

Listening to the mechanism of life through advanced polarized light microscopy

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Light microscope has been a major research tool for biomedical sciences for over 400 years. Among them, fluorescent single molecule imaging has provided dynamics of individual biological molecules in living cells at high spatial and temporal resolution. Studies involving super-resolution of fluorescently labeled molecules that have broken down the spatial resolution barrier of conventional light microscopy. We have enhanced these approaches by including the orientation dynamics of single molecules. The polarization of fluorescent labels can report the orientation of biomolecules as long as the labels are rigidly bound to the biomolecules, constraining their relative motion. Thus, monitoring the orientation of fluorescently labeled molecules is a powerful tool to detect the structural dynamics *in vitro* and in live cells. We have developed a new fluorescence polarization microscope that reports position and orientation dynamics of individual proteins in living cells. This microscope, the *instantaneous FluoPolScope*, (Mehta *et al.*, *PNAS* 2016, Swaminathan *et al.*, *PNAS*, 2017) is a synergetic combination of fluorescent single molecule detection, super-resolution localization microscopy, and polarized light imaging that allows tracking of position and orientation of individual fluorescent particles *in vitro* and in living cells. Our approach can provide new insights into questions raised by studies using high-resolution X-ray crystallography, NMR or electron microscopy about how micron-scale sub-cellular structures emerge from nano-scale molecular assemblies in live cells.

Aspiring Young
Researcher Session

AYR01:

Evaluation of in vitro fatigue properties of Mg-Ca alloy with fine grains

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Recently, magnesium alloys have attracted much attention as biomedical materials owing to its biodegradability and excellent biocompatibility. For application of the bone fixation devices, it is required to support the bone tissue during a few months which is exposed to body fluid and repeated loading. Since development of magnesium alloys with excellent fatigue properties in human body is preferable, this research conducted the evaluation of fatigue properties in simulated body fluid of Mg-Ca binary alloy with fine grains. Though cycles to failure remarkably increased at the fatigue test in air as decreasing grain size, there is little effect on the cycles to failure at the fatigue test in simulated body fluids.

Acknowledgement

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AYR02:

Climate variability and its ramification on river hydrology

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Large impacts of climate variations modes are found in the extremely low/high stream-flow events that are derived from the daily stream-flows of rivers from Indonesia, Brazil and India. Extreme events are identified based on their persistent flow for 5 days and more for the SON, DJF and JJA seasons for respective countries when the seasonal mean stream-flow are high. For Indonesia's Citarum River most of the extreme events of high-streamflows were related to La Niña conditions of tropical Pacific. A few of them were also associated with the negative phases of IOD and the newly identified El Niño Modoki. Unlike the cases of extreme high streamflows, extreme low streamflow events are seen to be associated with the positive IODs. Nevertheless, it was also found that the low-stream-flow events related to positive IOD events were also associated with El Niño events except for one independent event of 1977. Extremely-low discharge events of the Paranaíba River basin during the DJF season are found to be associated with the Pacific sea surface temperature anomalies resembling the recently identified El Niño Modoki phenomenon. Ninety percent of the extremely low discharge events during peak streamflow seasons of DJF, are found to occur during the El Niño Modoki years. A diagnostics study of atmospheric anomalies has shown a clear connection between the modified Walker circulation, associated with the El Niño Modoki, and the precipitation anomalies over the basin. Impact of climate variability modes on extreme events of Mahanadi basin during JJA season has been analysed, with daily Streamflow data of four gauge stations for 34 years from 1980 to 2013 and are found to be associated with the sea surface temperature variations over Indo-Pacific oceans and Indian monsoon. Flood frequency analysis with Weibull's plotting position method indicates future floods in the Mahanadi river basin in JJA season.

AYR03:

Multi-Connection VAWT: A Novel Solution to Harness Offshore Wind Energy

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Energy security is one of the biggest challenges in the 21st century. Clean and alternate forms of energy is the way forward to tackle climate change and its harmful effects. A holistic approach to energy is required to realize sustainable society both for the developed and developing world. The innovative solutions need to be scientifically reliable, technologically feasible, economically viable, socially and environmentally responsible.

Even though the ocean covers more than 70 percent of the earth’s surface, it has hardly been utilized to address energy issues. Ocean energy has the potential of providing a substantial amount of new renewable energy around the world. In this study, a new and innovative solution for harnessing offshore wind using vertical axis wind turbines (VAWT) is proposed and developed. Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT) is termed as Multi-Connection VAWT which uses single point mooring system and consists of turbines capable of aligning with wind direction. New-type vertical axis wind turbines are designed and developed which are supported by separate floaters. The conceptual development and working mechanism of the proposed Multi-Connection VAWT is demonstrated with two turbines based on experimental results. A numerical simulation code is also developed to understand the yaw motion around the moored point using the steering motion equations. It is confirmed how the new system proposed can be utilized for generating clean energy.

Experimental Model

Multi-Connection VAWT Concept

Poster Presentation

P01:

Tumors attenuating the mitochondrial activity in T cells escape from PD-1 blockade therapy.

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Immunotherapy mediated by PD-1 blockade has revolutionized the cancer treatments through its long-lasting effect and high efficacy against a wide variety of cancers with limited side-effects. However, only 40-50% patients are responsive to the PD-1 blockade therapy. To rescue the remaining unresponsive patients, it is imperative to understand the mechanism of unresponsiveness. Tumor-induced immunosuppression is one of the reasons of unresponsiveness. To test whether the unresponsive tumors suppress immune response, we devised a novel strategy (bilateral tumor model) where we can assess systemic immunosuppressive effect caused by unresponsive tumors on host's anti-tumor immune response against responsive tumor. We found some unresponsive tumors (e.g. B16, melanoma) do not suppress immune response while others (e.g. LLC, lung carcinoma) inhibit immune response in murine model. We observed the supernatant from suppressive tumors inhibits the T cells proliferation and mitochondrial function as well. It's uncharacterized, non-proteinaceous, and small molecule with size less than 3kDa. Since, activation of PGC1a/PPAR pathway using bezafibrate synergize with PD-1 blockade therapy through enhancing mitochondrial function and T cell proliferation, we performed bezafibrate combination therapy and found improved survival of immunosuppressive tumor-bearing hosts. In conclusion, for the first time using our established bilateral tumor model, unresponsive tumors can be categorized into immunosuppressive and non-immunosuppressive tumors based on secretion of soluble immunosuppressive factor that downregulate mitochondrial function and further improving mitochondrial function using mitochondrial activation chemicals improves the survival of immunosuppressive tumor-bearing hosts.

P02:

Engineering of genome editing protein Cas9 that slides along DNA faster and might enable efficient target search

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Genome editing protein Cas9 has been used in various biological studies; however, Cas9 has two defects: low efficiency and inaccuracy. Our earlier experiment based on single molecule fluorescence microscopy revealed that catalytically inactive Cas9 (dCas9), slides along DNA to much lesser extent than other DNA binding proteins. In this study, we tried to engineer dCas9 to slide along DNA faster by adding a sliding-promoting peptide. We analyzed the engineered dCas9 using single molecule fluorescence microscopy and DNA-aligned array, DNA garden. The engineered dCas9 showed enhancement of diffusion constant by three times relative to dCas9. This strategy may help in reducing target-DNA search time by Cas9 and might lead to precise and efficient gene editing in the future.

P03:

Designing Primitive Recursive Function based Domain Specific Programming Languages

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In today's technology-centric global landscape, software governs the functioning of every sector - from traditional spheres such as transportation to platforms of digital economy such as blockchain based cryptocurrencies. With the proliferation of domains and devices that use software today, the need to ensure software security has become more pertinent than ever. In the context of software, General purpose programming languages, that can be applied to diverse domains due to their rich features, such as C,C++,Python are known as "Turing complete languages" and are based on a mathematical model known as the 'Turing machine'. Along with rich computational features, Turing complete languages possess the following two properties: 1) Infinite memory 2) Ability to run a piece of code forever without terminating. While this may seem Utopian, in real world scenarios, there are finite computational requirements, hence, these properties of Turing Complete languages are both unnecessary for computations and also pose a number of security risks due to the possibility of infinite execution of code. For example, financially motivated attackers have exploited these properties in the cryptocurrency platform Ethereum, causing monetary losses upto 70M\$(2016). To counter these security vulnerabilities in existing languages that are currently used across multiple critical domains, there is a need to develop Domain Specific programming Languages(DSLs) with a focus on security. The goal of this research is to develop such a programming language that is devoid of critical software vulnerabilities existing in languages today and that can be applied to multiple target domains.

P04:

Simulation of particles evolution by mean curvature flow

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In various fields, e.g., in material science, properties of materials depend on the shape and size of small particles. In the case of a free particle with known surface energy, one can use the Wulff construction to find its equilibrium shape. However, when the particle is deposited on a rigid substrate, predicting the equilibrium shape is not trivial, especially when the surface energy is anisotropic. We consider a particle on a rigid substrate where the particle-vapor interface has orientation-dependent energy. In order to find its equilibrium shape, we design a simple evolution problem based on the gradient flow of the particle's surface energy, which is equivalent to the anisotropic mean curvature flow. To simulate the motion by mean curvature numerically, we use the level set approach based on diffusion-generated approximation (so-called BMO algorithm). We have developed an efficient algorithm to find the equilibrium shape of the particle on a substrate and proved the stability of the algorithm.

P05:

Patient-specific Bone Defect Reconstruction using Bioactive Filament through 3D Printing

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There is a huge demand of new biomaterials for the repair or regeneration of large segmental bone defects. The current tissue engineering approach is mainly focused on synthetic materials or bioactive ceramics for osteoinduction and angiogenesis but struggling to achieve required high mechanical properties. Herein we describe the application of a composite prepared from PCL (poly-caprolactone) a biocompatible and biodegradable polymer which is known for its mechanical property along with borate bioactive glass (BBG,1393-B3) in a filament form, for 3D printing with FDM (fuse deposition modeling) based printer. We prepared and characterized the borate bioactive glass, which demonstrated in-vitro mineralization. For the preparation of printable composite filament, firstly we prepared PCL & BBG slurry by mixing 0%, 25%, 50% & 75% (W/W%) of BBG in PCL and chloroform. Using doctor bleed casting, we prepared thin film (1mm thick) to perform swelling, degradation, pH test in PBS (phosphate buffer saline) and in-vitro mineralization in SBF (stimulated body fluid). The pellets prepared from this slurry has been served as an input material for filament preparation. This 3D printable PCL/BBG composite has the potential to serve as a biomaterial for patient specific bone defect reconstruction with high precision and accuracy.

P06:

Monitoring of Sand Deposition on PV Solar Panel Using Optical satellite data on Google Earth Engine

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There has been an exponential rise in solar power plants around the world. Soiling of solar panels is one of the factors which affect the overall efficiency of the solar power plant. This study focuses on detection and monitoring of sand deposition on photovoltaic (PV) solar panels in the desert region of India using remote sensing data. The study area is located in Bhadla solar park of Rajasthan, India which receive western and north-western wind carrying sand particles. The aim of this study is to use Google Earth Engine (GEE) in monitoring soiling phenomenon on the PV panels. Data acquisition and processing were done on GEE. This study discusses various methods and algorithms that can be used to monitor soiling of PV panels. Freely available Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 data were acquired from September 2017 till February 2019 for this study. Three types of sand indices were used to monitor test site viz. Normalized Differential Sand Index (NDSI), Ratio Normalized Differential Soil Index (RNDSI) and Dry Bare Soil Index (DBSI). Further, monitoring of temporal variation of soiling phenomenon were studied. Land Surface Temperature (LST) was also calculated to correlate and validate the existence of sand accumulation. Besides, high-resolution PlanetEarth satellite image was also used to visualize soiling area for validation. Use of freely available satellite data with semi-automated processing on GEE can be used to detect near real-time monitoring of soiling on PV panels cost-effectively. NDSI proved to be the most accurate method to detect sand deposition on PV panels. This study introduces use of handy Cloud-based technology for monitoring the factor that affects the power plant's overall performance.

P07:

Deformation behavior of TRIP-assisted multi-phase steels analyzed by *in-situ* X-ray Diffraction and Digital Image Correlation (DIC) method

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Transformation-induced-plasticity (TRIP) assisted multiphase steels have attracted significant interest for automotive applications due to their good mechanical balance between strength and ductility. In general, TRIP assisted multi-phase steels contain complex microstructure with ferrite, bainite, martensite and retained austenite phases. Although TRIP assisted multiphase steels show excellent mechanical properties, the detailed deformation behavior of different phases in the microstructures has not yet been clarified, because of their complicated microstructure. Recently, the *in-situ* X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Digital Image Correlation (DIC) method has been widely adopted for investigating strain of each phase in the microstructures. With the support of these advanced techniques, it is expected that the deformation nature of each phase in the multiphase steels can be evaluated. The objective of the present study is to investigate the deformation nature of each phase during deformation and to discuss the role of each phase on global mechanical properties of a TRIP assisted multiphase steel. The present study provides significant correlation between the stress partitioning, determined by HE-XRD and strain partitioning, estimated by μ -DIC method. During, the initial stages of, low-strain region, majority of the externally imposed strain is accommodated by newly formed martensite, predominantly due to the TRIP effect. In the later stages of strain, the strain localization is shifted to adjacent ferrite phases due to high strain hardening behaviour resulting from austenite to martensite transformation.

P08:

Common physiology of different host-parasitic plant complexes is controlled by mobile sRNAs

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Dodder (*Cuscuta* sp.), parasitic plant interacts with a wide range of hosts to uptake water and nutrients. Host-parasitic interaction makes a large scale of messenger RNAs, proteins and viruses exchange in a bi-directional manner. Dodder's microRNAs accumulate in interface tissue of host-parasitic complex to regulate host genes are also reported recently. However, the movement of small RNAs beyond interface tissue and their function to regulate the physiology of respective opponent plants is still unknown. Here, in this study, we analyze small RNAs (sRNAs) of different host-parasitic plant complexes (*Cuscuta japonica-Glycine max* and *Cuscuta campestris-Arabidopsis thaliana*) by sRNA-seq and screened the mobile sRNA candidates of both host and parasitic plants. The result shows that long-distance movement of sRNAs occurs bi-directionally. In parasitic plants, several mobile sRNAs are predicted to target orthologous genes of hosts such as *NIMA* (never in mitosis /Aspergillus) related kinase 3 (*Nek3*) which is involved in cell cycle regulation. Downregulation of the targeted host's genes, as well as its downstream genes, are confirmed in parasitic condition by qRT-PCR. Application of Locked-Nucleic Acids (LNA) design against *C. campestris* mobile sRNA which targets *AtNek3* can recover its expression similar to the non-parasitic level. The addition of artificial sRNA with LNA which can act as a competitor of the target site again shows the retardation of *AtNEK3* expression in parasitic conditions. Mobile sRNA may play a crucial role in physiological changes in host-parasitic plant complexes to maintain the parasitic relationship. This work was partly supported by the Cooperative Research Grant of the Genome Research for Bio-Resource (Tokyo University of Agriculture), the NIBB Cooperative Research Program (17-429) and KAKENHI (No.15H01237).

Keywords: Host-parasite interaction, Small RNA-seq, Small RNA, Long distance movement and qRT-PCR.

P09:

Site Reconnaissance of Long-Distance Ground Flow in Sulawesi, Indonesia due to September 28, 2018 Sulawesi Earthquake

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Abstract

This research presents the preliminary findings of site reconnaissance activities conducted aftermath the September 28, 2018 Sulawesi earthquake in Palu region in Central Sulawesi province in Sulawesi island of Indonesia. The Central Sulawesi province of Sulawesi island of Indonesia was trembled by a shallow earthquake of moment magnitude Mw 7.5 on 28th September 2018 at 18:02:44 local time. The event was preceded and succeeded by major foreshocks and aftershocks of significant magnitudes greater than moment magnitude Mw 5. The main shock was Epicentered in the mountainous Donggala regency of Minahasa peninsula of Central Sulawesi, approximately 70km from the provincial capital of Palu. It was first of its kind of earthquake event due to which long distance flow of soil mass, flow failure and mud flows were triggered in a very gentle sloping ground. The earthquake caused major geotechnical failures and structural damages in Palu city and Sigi regency along with thousands of deaths and many more injuries. Areas like Jono-Oge, Sibalaya, Petobo and Balaroa in the region were the worst hit by many long distance soil flow and mud flows. Due to the significant of event, the decision was made by the researchers from Kyushu university to organize engineering reconnaissance activities so as to collect perishable data to advance knowledge of earthquake induced geo-disasters, which ultimately leads to improved procedures for characterization and mitigation of geo-hazard risk. This research gives an insight on the magnitude of ground failure and other infrastructural damages caused by the event in Palu city, Donggala and Sigi regency. The preliminary findings made from in-situ field tests (PDCPT) and aerial drone (UAV) photography during the reconnaissance survey are depicted.

P10:

Identification of the Inhibitory Activity of HIV-1 Reverse Transcriptase in the Extracts of Indian Plants

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India has 3rd largest population of people living with HIV in the world. Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) reverse transcriptase (RT) which is responsible for causing AIDS has DNA polymerase activities and RNase H activity that helps in the replication of virus. Today, development of a novel and inexpensive HIV-1 RT inhibitor is anticipated. Combined with the Indian traditional Ayurveda system, a plant extract with HIV-1 RT inhibitory activity might be developed as a novel and inexpensive pharmaceutical in AIDS treatment [1].

In this study, we screened for HIV-1 RT inhibitory activity in various extracts of 5 Indian plants, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *Argemone mexicana*, *Solanum xanthocarpum*, *Calotropis procera*, and *Thevetia peruviana*. Water-extracts from leaf of *Argemone Mexicana* strongly inhibited the DNA polymerase activity of HIV-1 RT, indicating that it probably contains a compound that inhibits the activity. Neither thermal treatment at 100°C nor proteinase K treatment of the extracts affects the inhibitory activity, signifying that the inhibitory substance is likely to be an organic compound rather than a protein.

Figure 1. Inhibition of HIV-1 RT activity by 20 extracts. (A) Origin and preparation method of the extracts. R and H indicates room temperature and temperatures equivalent to the boiling point of the respective solvents, respectively. (B) HIV-1 RT activity in the presence of extracts. The results of the assay using $[^3\text{H}]\text{-dTTP}$ and using fluorescent dye PicoGreen are shown.

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P11:

Targeted suppression of the metastasis regulatory transcription factor SOX2 in various cancer cell lines using a sequence-specific designer pyrrole–imidazole polyamide

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SOX2, though initially known as pluripotency-associated transcription factor and essential during embryogenesis, but its expression in later life is detrimental. Past few years has shown tremendous research for SOX2 implication in many human cancers. Its role has been implicated in many cancers for tumorigenicity, malignancy, invasiveness, metastasis, high proliferation and drug resistance. Recently, small molecules got proclaimed to cancer therapies. N-Methylpyrrole (Py) and N-methylimidazole (Im) are noncovalent hairpin polyamides which selectively recognize Watson–Crick base pairs of DNA sequences located within the minor groove that modulate endogenous gene expression. We have developed sequence-specific designer PIPs (SOX2i, hereinafter) that bind with conserved sequence (from mouse to human) in SOX2 promoter region and inhibit the transcription/translation of master transcription factor SOX2. SOX2i significantly inhibits the expression of SOX2 at mRNA and protein level in human cancer cell lines e.g. MKN45 (gastric adenocarcinoma), MCF7 (breast carcinoma), U2OS (osteosarcoma) and SW620 (colorectal adenocarcinoma) and many others of different origin and type. SOX2 inhibition has been evidenced by i) reduced proliferation ii) reduced migration and invasion in a dose-dependent manner. Genome-wide expression analysis shows SOX2 to be downregulated upstream regulator. Since SOX2i targets conserved sequence from mouse to human in SOX2 promoter region, we tested the effect of PIP in mouse metastasis melanoma model and found reduction in metastatic nodules in the treated group. In summary, the designer PIP inhibits the SOX2 which results in reduced proliferation, invasiveness, migration *in vitro* and metastasis *in vivo* which shows its therapeutic importance for cancer treatment.

P12:

Characterization of a novel sub-family of rhodopsin (Heliorhodopsin), spectral tuning and anion binding to counterion mutants in 48C12

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Recently, through functional metagenomics analysis, we reported an unnoticed diverse family, heliorhodopsins (HeRs), which are abundant and distributed globally in archaea, bacteria, eukarya, and viruses. The sequence identity is <15% between HeRs and type 1 rhodopsins, so that many aspects of the molecular properties of HeRs remain unknown. We applied Ala scanning to 30 candidate residues in HeR 48C12. Out of which, 12 mutants showed no absorption change, 8 mutants exhibited a spectral blue-shift, six exhibited a spectral red-shift, and four did not form a pigment. Heliorhodopsin, contains single counterion i.e. Glu-107, which corresponds to HeR 48C12. We examined possible anion binding to the wild-type (WT) and Glu-107 mutants of HeR 48C12. We screened three mutants Glu107Ala, Glu107Gln, and Glu107Asn and anion binding was tested by using UV-visible spectroscopy. The experimental results clearly revealed no anion (Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, and NO₃⁻) binding in case of WT and Glu107Asp. On the other hand, anion binding was observed to the Schiff base region in Glu107Ala and Glu107Gln. Similar halide-size dependency on the absorption spectra of the chromophore in solution strongly suggests that the anion acted as the direct hydrogen-bonding acceptor of the protonated Schiff base in Glu107Ala. In the case of Glu107Gln, small spectral shift on the small halide dependence, we interpreted the C=O group of Gln107 side chain as the hydrogen-bonding acceptor. The two mutants Glu107Ala and Glu107Gln existed as a pH-dependent equilibrium mixture of PSB (Visible form) and SB (Near-UV form). Moreover, the anion binding stabilized the protonated state without a direct hydrogen bond with the Schiff base.

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P13:**Biomass derived hard carbons as anode for sodium ion batteries****Alisha Yadav**

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The era of wide-scale implementation of renewable energy sources like sun, wind, hydrothermal energy etc., calls the urge for inexpensive and efficient energy storage systems for the smooth integration of these intermittent energies into stationary as well as grid application. Though the Li-ion batteries (LIBs) have become essential in everyday technology, the problems like safety, lifetime, poor low-temperature performance, non-ideal for grid-scale energy storage, less abundance of Li resources, cost etc. are still prevailing. To overcome these issues, Na-ion batteries (NIBs) have been attained a considerable interest in the recent years as a possible alternative to LIBs. The advantages of natural abundance, low cost, similar chemical properties like Li and comparative redox potential (2.714 V vs. Na/Na⁺) of Na compared with Li (3.06 V vs. Li/Li⁺), making NIBs as a promising alternative to LIBs for large-scale energy storage systems and sustainable applications. Even though Na and Li have comparative redox potential, and the same valence of lithium, the volume of sodium ions is ~2 times more than that of lithium and ~3 times in terms of atomic weight. Therefore, sodium-based materials are disadvantageous to lithium-based materials in terms of energy density. Besides, the current versions have a very low capacity and cycle life. The conventional anodes for LIBs such as graphite and Si based materials are found to be badly inefficient as anodes for NIBs. Hence, hard carbon is used as the anode (Na_xC₆), in Na-ion cells. In the present study, I have used rice husk for the synthesis of hard carbon. Rice husk is a biowaste and is easily available so the synthesis process is economical and easy. The hard carbons have been synthesized by acid activation and pyrolysis of rice husk at different carbonization temperatures (700, 900, 1100^oc). The three samples that are prepared are ARH-700, ARH-900 and ARH-1100. The phase structure of the synthesized hard carbon sample was characterized by recording the X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern. The crystalline structures of the carbons are further characterized by Raman spectroscopy analysis. The morphology of the synthesized hard carbon sample was studied using SEM analysis which confirms the presence disordered structure of hard carbons. The electrochemical studies were carried out and it was found that ARH-1100 shows the best performance with initial irreversible capacity of 735 mAhg⁻¹ and the first charging capacity of 335 mAhg⁻¹.

In summary, a successful strategy was developed for the synthesis of hard carbons from rice husk. The structure and morphology of the synthesized hard carbon samples were confirmed from the obtained XRD, Raman and SEM results. All the activated rice husks were found to show good properties. The excellent charge/discharge capacities and superior rate capability of the developed NIB, made up of the synthesized hard carbon anode, were obtained from the cyclic voltammetry, charge-discharge and electrochemical impedance responses. The high capacity retention of the ARH-1100 (270 mAh g⁻¹ even after 70 cycles)

may be attributed to the optimized interlayer spacing, graphitic nature and the reduced number of pores and defects. Hence, obtained results show that the biomass derived hard carbon could be a better anode material for NIB applications due to its facile synthesis procedure and sustainable resource. The present work also gives a new insight into the high value-added usage of biomass wastes. A series of hard carbons could be simply prepared from other biomass also through the reported synthesis strategy. The initial discharge capacities observed for all the carbon samples i.e., ARH-700, ARH-900 and ARH-1100 are 950 mAh/g, 802 mAh/g and 735 mAhg⁻¹ respectively. Both cycling curves and CV show irreversible capacity loss for the first cycle due to SEI formation but after subsequent cycles both the profiles almost overlap, indicating that the capacity decay mainly occurs in the first cycles, and subsequently the carbon shows good Na ion insertion-extraction reversibility and cycle stability. After cycling of cells at high current density, followed by cycling at low current density of 300 mA g⁻¹, the cells retain almost 95 % capacity indicating the improved capacity retention at the high current densities. The charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) values are decreasing with increase in the number charge/discharge cycles. The decrease in R_{ct} values after cycling suggests the fast charge transfer process occurring upon continuous cycling. Hence, we can use rice husk or biomass to produce hard carbons by following easy and economical procedures to generate batteries which can be used immediately for various purposes in daily life.

P14:

Seismic response analysis of Full-scale test specimen of E-Defense shake table

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Recent advancement in High Performance Computing (HPC) has enabled researchers to perform the high-fidelity Finite Element (FE) analysis using solid elements. On the same line thoughts, E-Simulator is being developed at-and-by E-Defense of NIED, which aims to reproduce the damage mechanism of civil structures exposed to the any sort of strong ground motions. E-Simulator is parallel FE analysis tool, which uses a general-purpose parallel FE software: ADVENTURECluster, as a platform to accomplish the large-scale simulations. Schemes such as hierarchical domain decomposition method for domain decomposition in linear algebraic solver, coarse grid conjugate gradient (CGCG) method; an iterative solver and Hilbert-Hughes-Taylor time integration scheme aka α -method are incorporated.

Sophisticated constitutive models and failure criterions for various materials such as concrete, steel and rubber, with the appropriate mathematical framework are included in the tool. It is noteworthy to mention that every crucial stage involved in the large-scale simulation is verified and validated with experimental data.

In this talk, I would like to briefly introduce the capabilities of E-Simulator by demonstrating the few simulations of namely composite beam (i.e. steel beam with concrete slab) -to-column T-joint, soil-underground structure specimen and furniture's set-ups tested at E-Defense, accomplished using this tool.

P15:

Phenylketonuria inspired amino acid self-assembly model and its applications

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Non covalent interactions amongst amino acids in a polypeptide chain have been known to play an important role in governing the structure of a protein. These non-covalent interactions have been the reason for the desired folding or miss folding of the protein. For years, the miss-folded proteins have been intensively studied for understanding the supramolecular construct responsible for neurodegenerative diseases and designing their inhibitors.

However, for a long time, the neurodegenerative disease caused due to single amino acid i.e. phenylketonuria (PKU) had been neglected. Phenylketonuria is caused by the superamolecular assemblies of phenylalanine (Phe) and the generation of antibodies against Phe confirms the toxicity of the amino acid fibrils. In the present study, amino acid assembly of other amino acids are under investigation to understand the role of non-covalent interactions and to design non canonical and/or derivatised amino acid for applications. The site specific modification for designing amino acid vesicle for oral drug delivery will be discussed as it will be a greener and enzymatically stable approach over the present literature.

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